

The Concept Of Good And Ross's Ethical Theory: A Philosophical Analysis

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Abstract

The issues of worthy actions has been an aged long debate in our daily routine, scholars have argued that a philosophical study of morality is much more different from other related field such as anthropological or sociological study or even a study from the perspective of psychology or biology, it is often observed that people come, early and easily, to think in moral term, sees many things as good or bad, view various option as right or wrong, think of particular distributions as fair or unfair, consider certain people virtuous and others vicious. Most often, in thinking in this direction has a large contribution on their actions and decisions also on their reactions to what other people do which can be structured by considerations of religion, law, professional code of conducts, traditions, custom or self-interest. The question therefore arises, what distinguishes moral consideration from other kinds, what does morality require, what kinds of actions are good or bad, right or wrong, does morality determine what we ought to do, how should we live our live or lives. In this paper, the method of analysis is adopted in the quest to philosophical analyze the concept of good and that of Ross's ethical theory. It concludes that understanding the idea of good and a critical look at the principles one can affirm that Ross's argument on rightness and goodness of actions will create a very positive instinct in man for the betterment of society.

Keyword: Philosophy, Good, Ethical theory, Morality, Concept, Analysis.

Preamble:

Over the years, scholars have argued that the issues of ethics known as a philosophical study of morality is much more different from other related field such as anthropological or sociological study or even a study from the perspective of psychology or biology as noted by Copp (2006 p.5) philosophers, scholars are of the opinion because in moral philosophy, we do not isolates ourselves from our moral views or stand in the way we would if we are engaged in a study of these other discipline. In strengthening the above assertion, Copp (2006 p. 5) writes that: We do not take the fact that people, including ourselves, have moral views as merely a datum to be explained. Our goal is not the distribution of moral beliefs and attitudes or the occurrence of selfish

or altruistic actions rather in moral philosophy, the correctness, cogency or defensibility of moral claims, convictions, attitudes and the probity of various behaviours are among the things at issue.

The issues of good and bad which falls under the branch of philosophy known as ethics is usually discussed from three major angles or viewpoints namely, normative, meta and that of applied ethics. Normative ethics by a of description is the study of what makes action right or wrong, what makes situations or events good or bad and what makes virtuous or vicious. On the other hand, meta-ethics deals on the attempt to answer the fundamental philosophical questions about what the nature of the ethical theory itself while that of applied ethics consist in pursuit of solving or proffering solution to the moral questions people actually faces in their day to day actives. Normative ethics makes moral claims in its own right. Meta-ethics does not do this, yet despite this, it is morally engaged for among its central questions are the questions whether any moral claims are true, whether it is rational to commit oneself to acting morally.

Again, it is often observed that people come, early and easily, to think in moral term, sees many things as good or bad, view various option as right or wrong, think of particular distributions as fair or unfair, consider certain people virtuous and others vicious. Most often, in thinking in this direction has a large contribution on their actions and decisions also on their reactions to what other people do.

People usually let go some attractive things when they think or sees that pursuing them would be wrong, they push themselves to face death like in the case of Socrates if they think it is their duty, some people pursue things they take to be valuable, train their children to be virtues. Also have a high regard those who are courageous and condemn people they judge to be unjust, with all these, one may see moral thinking as one of the vital aspect our lives. Yet when people ask themselves honestly what it is they are thinking in thinking some acts are right and others wrong, that some things are good, others bad, that some character traits are virtues, other vices, it turns out to be extremely difficult to say. This raises a puzzle that is at the centre of our understanding of our selves and of our understanding of morality.

Geoffrey (2006 p. 43) pointed out that focusing just on the question of what it is for something to be good, for instance, some people have maintained that to be good is simply to be pleasant while others have held that what is good is whatever that satisfies a desire or perhaps a desire we desire to have. And still others have argued that for something to be good is for it to be such that a fully informed person would approve of it, but this concept of good is usually viewed

by many scholars as the most general term of positive evaluation used to recommend or express approval in a wide range of contexts. It indicates that a thing is desirable or worthy of choice so that normally, if you have reason to want a certain kind of thing, you also have reason to prefer a good thing of that kind.

Korsgaard (2011) viewing the idea of good from the angle of the language use maintained that a theory of the good may consist in a general account of the good, which is meant to apply to all good things; or in a definition of 'good', that is, an account of how the term functions in the language. Theories of the good have metaphysical implications about the relations between fact and value. In elucidation, Korsgaard (2011) noted that philosophers or Theorists of the good also categorize different kinds of goodness or views it from different perspectives and explain how they are related. Good things are standardly classified as ends, which are valued for their own sakes, or as means, valued for the sake of the ends they promote. Some scholars also divide them into intrinsic goods, which have their value in themselves, and extrinsic goods, which get their value from their relation to something else. Various theories have been held about the relation between these two distinctions about whether an end must be something with intrinsic value. Philosophers also distinguish subjective or agent-relative goods (things which are good for someone in particular) from objective or agent-neutral goods, (which are good from everyone's point of view). Views about how these kinds of goodness are related have important implications for moral philosophy.

Many ancient and medieval philosophers believed in the ultimate identity of the real and the good. Modern philosophers generally reject this identification, and have held a range of positions: Emotivists hold that we use the term 'good' only to signify subjective approval. While realists, for example, hold that the good is part of reality, while certain moral-sense theorists hold that when we call something 'good' we are projecting human interests onto reality; and Usually, a theory of the good is constructed with the hope of shedding light on more substantive questions, such as what makes a person, an action, or a human life good. These questions raise issues about the relation between ethical and other values. For example, we may ask whether moral virtue is a special sort of goodness, or just the ordinary sort applied to persons. Or, since actions are valued as 'right' or 'wrong', we may ask, how these values are related to the goodness or badness of an action. We may also pose the question of whether a life that is good in the sense of being happy must also be a morally good or virtuous life.

The Concept of Good: A Historical Perspective

The subject matter of good started in the early Greece with the debate of good and evil, what constitutes good life for man, Philosophers like Heraclitus, Democritus, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Hobbes, Kant, Moore and Ross to mention but a few have asked the question, is there an absolute, ultimate, and unquestioned measure of good and bad, right and wrong e.t.c. one that was established at the beginning of time and that will stand until time is no more?.

Stumpf (2003 pp.15-18) Heraclitus the Greek philosopher of change, believed that good and evil were two notes of harmony. He observed that many things are changing into their opposites. For him, fire itself exhibits this tension of opposite, in the one many find their unity, the way up and the way down are the same good and ill are one. For instance, Ice, which is hard changes into water, which is soft. This led him to believe that the combination of opposites resulted in a whole in which there is harmony. Again, just as in music harmony results from the combination of low and high notes, so in the universe harmony results from the combination of opposites, good and evil. Thus, the good life for man is that life lived in harmony with the universal reason (God), the law which pervades all things. He concludes that man should seek to understand this harmony in the universe and to fit into it so as that his actions are in accord with the principle governing the whole universe because to God all things are fair, good and right.

Stumpf (2003 p. 28) Democritus, the leading figure of the Greek Atomists besides describing the structure of nature concerned himself with two philosophical problem, the problem of knowledge and the problem of human conduct. According to him “man at all times should seek for happiness”. He thought the goal of life to be happiness because happiness is the inner condition or state of tranquility which depended upon harmony of the soul, He taught that one should not depend for happiness upon things of the world since these come and go and a lack of them causes unhappiness. Rather, happiness should be a state of inner man, a balance of life, an attitude which combines reflection and reason. Goodness, for him, was not only a matter of action but depended upon man’s inner desire. The good man is not one who does good, but one who wants to do good at all times. “you can tell the man who rings true from the man who rings false,” such goodness brings happiness, the goal of life.

Peter Singer (2020) Socrates was said to have been influenced by the Sophists but was unwilling to go all the way with them. Socrates been interested in the problems related to living a good life. . Stumpf (2003 p.42) Socrates maintained that knowledge and virtue were the same. If

virtue has to with making the soul as good as possible, then it becomes necessary to know what makes the soul good, with this, he concludes that goodness and knowledge are closely related which made him to argue that if one knows what is right, he will do it. “No man he said is voluntarily bad”. When one knows that a thing is good he will choose to do that thing. Therefore the most important endeavour of man is to discover what is good. He spent his life trying to help man discover what is good. Thus, for him, a life which is always inquiring and trying to discover what is good is the best kind of life, the only life worth living.

Plato took up the problem of good and evil where Socrates stopped. For him, goodness is tied up with his theory of universe. The world of sense, he thought, is unreal, fleeting, changing. This is evil for him. The real world of pure, unchanging ideas is the world of good. Man can only know this real world only through reason. Therefore, reason is the highest good for man. The end or goal of life is release of the soul from the body so that it can contemplate the true world of ideas. Thus, a life of reason is “the highest good for man, a life noted for wisdom, courage, and self-control”. For Plato, this kind of life will be the happy life because happiness and goodness go together. However, one should not seek pleasure as the end of life, pleasure comes when one has attained the good life, a life in which the highest reason rules the lower will and appetites.

Aristotle pointed out that every action of man has some end in view and that these ends seem to be an endless chain. One acts in order to get something, but this thing is obtained in order to get something else, and so on. What, he asked, is the highest good, the good for which all else is done. He reached an answer to this question by pointing out that the aim of everything in the universe is to realize itself to the fullest. Each thing is deferent from all others. It has certain talents and abilities. Thus it is good when it has realized these talents and abilities to the fullest. Thus, self realization is for Aristotle the highest good, the goal of all else that is done.

Now, the distinguishing feature of man is his reason. No other entity in the universe possesses reason. Man alone has this characteristic ability. Therefore, the highest good of man is the complete realization of his reason. This, Aristotle believed, brings happiness. Pleasure accompanies the full realization of man’s reason, it is a natural result of such realization. What is this rational attitude? Aristotle taught that it consisted of the “Golden Mean”. For example, courage is to be thought of as a mean between cowardice and foolhardiness. The good man is one who lives a life according to the golden mean, who does not go to extremes in action but balances one extreme against other.

Ross's Ethical Theory

The debates of good and what makes something good has been the interest of moral philosophy. Scholars from antiquity have discussed the issue of the good from different perspectives. W.D Ross's pluralist approach marked the pinnacle of ethical intuitionism which is a doctrine that had been the dominant moral theory in Britain for much of the preceding two hundred years. Ross a moral realist whose principles are based on metaphysics of morals, normative ethics and moral epistemology. Ross argued that rightness and goodness are objective features of the world in just the way that shape, size and mass are. Ross (2007. P.x) This made him to assert that: There is a system of moral truth as objective as all truth must be. We do not make actions right or good by our moral attitudes, conventions, culture or whatever any more than we make same thing square in these ways. Rather our mind attitudes are responses to perceived goodness or rightness.

Ross (2007 pp. x-xii) argued further that when we do appropriate things, that is, things we are supposed or obliged to do, we do it because we believe and think that it is the way it ought to be. By this, we ask ourselves is it really good, bad, right or wrong to do these things? Ross made it emphatically clear, that what makes our moral belief that X is good true (when it is true) is a property or objective characteristic X has of being good. He was also of the view that even when all of the empirical facts are in, there is still a further moral judgment to be made namely that empirical facts make a certain act right or good.

However, Ross insisted that rightness and goodness are non natural properties rather they are simple properties. That rightness means that they are not combinations of two or more properties or relations such as the relation of being appropriate (moral) and the property of being approved (non moral) or the causal relation (non moral) and the property of being best (moral). In his normative theory Ross defends a form of methodological intuitionism. Methodological intuitionism maintained that there is a plurality of first principles that may conflict and that no explicit priority rules for resolving such conflicts can be provided. This pluralism applies not only to the right but to the good also. He maintained that there is no single source of morality but several because there are several Prima-Facie Duties that we can use to determine what concretely we ought to do. This prima-facie duty is a duty that is binding (obligatory) other things equal, that is, unless it is overridden or trumped by another duty or duties and what we must do after balancing all the conflicting prima facie duties we may have. Another way of putting it is, that where there

is a prima facie duty to do something, there is at least a fairly strong presumption in favour of doing it unless stronger moral considerations override prima facie duty. Rob (2009 pp.101-107)

The Ross Prima Facie Duties includes:

- ❖ Duties of Fidelity: There are duties stemming from our explicit and implicit promises. That is, duties to keep one's promises and contracts and not to engage in deception.
- ❖ Duties of Reparation: These are duties stemming from our past wrong-doings towards others. Ross describes this duty as "resting on a previous wrongful act".
- ❖ Duties of Gratitude: These are duties to repay or redo favours or simply thank others for their kindness.
- ❖ Duties of Justice and Fairness: These are duties involving distribution of goods and services in a fair and equal manner whenever possible.
- ❖ Duties of Beneficence: These are duties to try to bring about the happiness of other people if possible.
- ❖ Duties of Self-improvement: These are duties involving making the best of ourselves and making our lives the best they could be.
- ❖ Duties of Non-maleficence: These are duties not to hurt, harm or sadden other people.

Critical Examination of Ross Ethical Theory

It has been argued that the most central aspects of human beings is that we can engage in significant deliberation and practical reasoning. In deliberation, we consider and weigh reasons for and against various courses of action. We seek to figure out what is best to do, and to act in accordance with this sort of judgments, about what is best to do, all things considered. In maintaining this traditional thought patterns it will be paramount to critically examine Ross ethical idea there by bringing out the strengths and weakness the theory.

Bernard (1968.p.237) pointed out that Strawson attacked Ross ethical principles of promise keeping as an inconsistent on the ground that keeping promise is not categorically right but only prima facie right, not only that, even the proposition expressing the judgment all acts of promise-keeping are prima facie right is a necessary synthetic proposition.

Thomas (2005 p.149) Ross's ethical theory has been criticized on the basis of moral knowledge which is idea of "The Moral Convictions of Thoughtful and Well-Educated People", Ross notes that the moral convictions of thoughtful and well-educated people

can conflict. For instance, your moral convictions may tell you that it is morally permissible to lie in order to spare someone mild embarrassment, whereas mine tell me that it is wrong to lie simply for that reason. There is no single comprehensive set of moral beliefs that is accepted by all thoughtful and well-educated people. Ross is aware of this problem and notes that we must find some way to eliminate the conflict between different people's moral beliefs. He says that we must reject those moral beliefs that conflict with other moral beliefs that better stand the test of reflection, but he does not spell out what this involves or give any examples of how this might be done.

Thomas (2005 p. 148) noted again that another lacuna is also noticeable in his argument of "Self-Evident Knowledge of moral principle". The phenomenon of moral disagreement raises serious problems for Ross's claim that we have "self-evident" knowledge of basic moral principles. Because certain moral principles claimed to be self-evident by some people are rejected by others. Disagreement alone does not undermine Ross's claims, but disagreement among competent or "expert" moral appraisers creates serious problems for Ross. Agreement among competent and expert judges makes possible much of our knowledge. Without this agreement, we may fully trust our own sensory and cognitive capacities. For example, our knowledge of the things around us is dependent on the extent of inter-subjective agreement in reports about our environment by those with properly functioning sensory organs. If my observations of the world were frequently contradicted by the observations of others, I may not rely on them to nearly the extent that I am able to.

On the other hand, out of these criticisms which emerge a distinct moral position, emphasizing the complexity of moral life. Burgh (1931 p.236) asserts that the Ross work on the Right and the Good is a masterly essay on what is perhaps the most difficulty group of problems in moral philosophy, for him it is masterly design in argument and in expression, he states his views without a trace of dogmatism and bases his conclusions on careful examination of the evidence and with full discussion of relevant objections. Bernard (1968.p 238) in defending Ross of the attack on the principle by Strawson stated that Ross does not explain *prima facie* as interpreted by Strawson. Ewig (1940 p. 85) in a review of Foundations of Ethics, asserts that Ross work: The Foundations of ethics displays the characteristics of detailed care and precision, fairness in controversy, lucidity and clear insight into the ethical situation that we should all expect from Sir David Ross, and may be heartily commended to students of ethics. Some will no doubt

regret the absence of any mention, even as illustrations, of the terrible practical ethical problems which were agitating the world....we can certainly all learn much from what is the fullest treatment of ethics as a pure science...

Strengthening the argument for the scholarly contribution of Ross work, Broad (1940 P.228) writes that *The Right and the Good* was 'much the most important contribution to ethical theory made in England for a generation'. The best explanation of Broad's praise is that the book presents a unique and compelling form of deontology, according to which there are a plurality of both moral requirements and intrinsic goods. There is no one master principle that explains why particular things that we believe are wrong/right are in fact wrong/right. Instead, there are a number of basic moral requirements which cannot be reduced to some more fundamental principle. These are relied upon in making decisions about what we ought to do all things considered, though there is no sense in which this is deduced from principles. There is no one intrinsic good/evil that explains why particular things we think are good/evil are in fact good/evil. Instead, there are a number of goods which cannot be reduced to some more fundamental good. These are relied upon in making decisions about the goodness or badness of a state of affairs all things considered, though there is no sense in which this is deduced from these claims. It is his articulation of this particular view that makes Ross's work a lasting philosophical contribution.

Ross (2012) Ross is said to have been one of the selected number of modern intellectuals who made important and lasting contributions to two different academic fields: in his case, In the case of ethics, Ross occupies a well-deserved place in the long and distinguished line of British moral philosophers in the analytical-critical tradition, a group that includes such important names as Bentham, Mill, Sidgwick, Moore, Prichard, Hare, and Ayer. *The Right and the Good*, his critique of ideal utilitarianism and exposition of his own deontological system, remains a classic text and a key document in the history of modern ethical theory, influencing later revisions or variations of intuitionism by Philip Stratton-Lake, Robert Audi, Michael Huemer, and others. C.D. Broad called the book "the most important contribution to ethical theory made in England in a generation" and applauded Ross for applying his considerable "good sense, acuteness, and clarity" to "elucidating questions of perennial significance."

In the area of classical studies, his signal achievement was undoubtedly his editorship of the "Oxford," the 11-volume English translation of Aristotle's complete works that ignited a renewal of interest in the philosopher throughout the English-speaking world and to which he

himself contributed elegant translations of the *Metaphysics* and the *Nicomachean Ethics*. One of the important secondary effects of this renewed interest in Aristotle was the re-discovery and eventual re-flourishing of virtue ethics during the second half of the 20th century. This powerful revival of virtue theory and eudaimonism would have been practically impossible if it had not been prepared and facilitated decades earlier by the appearance of the Oxford.

Concluding Reflections

In this paper, the examination of the idea of good were made, starting with the notes that the philosophical study of morality differs from that of other disciplines, as well as the understanding of the term good from different authors, scholars and philosophers. In doing this, the work traces the origin of the debates of what good is and what is not, in the bid to get rid of the ambiguity of the term, and it was discovered that it is a perennial problem which started with the debates of what constitutes good life. From the Greek Heraclitus, a philosopher of change in his theory upholds that good and evil were two notes of harmony, he observed that many things are changing into their opposite, thus the good life for man is that life lived in harmony with the universal reason “God”, the law which pervades all things.

According to Democritus, the leading figure of the Greek Atomists theory sees the aim of life to be happiness, man at all times should seek for happiness. Because happiness is the inner condition or state of tranquility which depended upon harmony of the soul, He taught that one should not depend for happiness upon things of the world since these come and go and a lack of them causes unhappiness.

Socrates on his part was stimulated by the Sophists but was unwilling to go all the way with them. Socrates been interested in the problems related to living a good life. What is the highest good by which all else in the universe is measured? And his answer was that knowledge is the highest good. Thus, for him, a life which is always inquiring and trying to discover what is good is the best kind of life, the only life worth living.

For Plato, the idea of good or goodness can only be seen in the real world of pure and unchanging ideas which can only be known through reason, thus he sees reason as the highest good for man.

Again Aristotle argued that every action of man has some end in view and that these ends seem to be an endless chain. One acts in order to get something, but this thing is obtained in order to get something else, and so on. He sees what man asked as the highest good which is self

realization. Thus man act is good when he has realized these talents and abilities to the fullest. Thus, self realization is for Aristotle the highest good, the goal of all else that is done. Through the rational attitude consisting the “Golden Mean”. Upon this principle, he concludes that a good man is one who lives a life according to the golden mean, who does not go to extremes in his action but balances one extreme over against other.

Tracing the idea of good down to Ross theory which is the bedrock of this paper, it was also noted that Ross in his normative theory defends a form of methodological intuitionism which maintained that there is a plurality of first principles that may conflict and that no explicit priority rules for resolving such conflicts can be provided. This pluralism applies not only to the right but to the good also. He maintained that there is no single source of morality but several because there are several Prima-Facie Duties that we can use to determine what concretely we ought to do. This prima-facie duty as aforementioned is a duty that is binding (obligatory) other things equal, that is, unless it is overridden or trumped by another duty or duties and what we must do after balancing all the conflicting prima facie duties we may have. This Ross’s theory has its strength and weakness as observed above, but even at that, a critical look at the principles one can affirm that Ross’s argument on rightness and goodness of actions will create a very positive instinct in man especially his idea on Prima-Facie duties, it will make an impact on the individuals in our society by wakening the moral goodness up and limiting the dogmatic slumberness of consciousness. The conscious mind will always be awake and alert to the positive principles of moral goodness. The moral decadence in the society is becoming unbearable; this is because many do not know what values and norms are all about. Many people are highly influenced by social stratifications, ethnicity, tribalism, racism, peer pressure, bad westernization e.t.c, without looking critically into the different dimensions of such acts, thought or beliefs system. It is hoped that the adoption and the application of these Ross’s principles and its inculcation as guiding principle in the day to day activities of mankind, this paper argued will make a better society for the benefit of all especially when implemented in all spheres of life.

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